

Thermal Decomposition and Kinetics of Dehydration of Neodymium(III) and Gadolinium(III) Tartarates

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Tartarates of Nd^{III} and Gd^{III}, i.e. Nd₂C₁₂H₁₂O₁₈·3H₂O and Gd₂C₁₂H₁₂O₁₈·7H₂O have been prepared and characterised by metal analysis and infrared spectra. The thermal decomposition of these compounds shows the pattern of decomposition to be uniform, the first step leading to the formation of anhydrous salts. In the subsequent stages, conversion to the corresponding oxalates is observed. In case of gadolinium compound, partial conversion to basic carbonate occurs. The final product of decomposition in both the cases is the oxide, Nd₂O₃ and Gd₂O₃.

The thermogravimetric data for the first step of decomposition has been computer-analysed for the evaluation of kinetic parameters (non-isothermal method) as also for arriving at the mechanism of dehydration involved in the process. The equations of Piloyan and Novikova, Coats and Redfern, and Horowitz and Metzger have been applied. Reasonable values of *E*, *Z* and ΔS^\ddagger have been obtained. The results indicate that dehydration proceeds according to random nucleation mechanism.

THE thermal decomposition of metal carboxylates¹⁻⁸ has been attracting considerable interest due to the wide range of applications of these compounds and their decomposition products. However, the work on the thermal decomposition of tartarates^{4,5}, particularly the kinetics of their thermal decomposition is very scanty. The present paper conveys the results of the thermogravimetric analysis and kinetics of thermal dehydration of tartarates of Nd^{III} and Gd^{III}.

Experimental

The compounds were prepared by mixing aqueous solution (30 ml) containing the respective rare earth metal chloride (Indian Rare Earths, 99.9% pure) (0.01 mol) with aqueous solution (30 ml) containing tartaric acid (Merck, proanalysis) (0.01 mol) in presence of some pyridine (Ranbaxy A.R., 99.5% pure) at room temperature.

Pyridine was added with a view to obtain pyridinium salts. However, it was found even on repeating the process, that the resulting compounds did not contain any pyridine, in stead the compounds formed were the tartarates, as reported here. The presence of pyridine seems to control the pH of the solution to that required in the preparation. No compound was obtained in the absence of pyridine. The fine crystalline precipitates of the compounds were separated by filtration, washed with distilled water and air-dried.

The percentage of the metals was determined gravimetrically by precipitating as Nd(OH)₃ and Gd(OH)₃ and weighing as Nd₂O₃ and Gd₂O₃, respectively. The infrared spectra (KBr) were

carried out on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer in the range 4 000–400 cm⁻¹. The thermogravimetric measurements were carried out on a Mettler TA-3000 system (Switzerland) at a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹ in the atmosphere of air. The TG and DTG curves were recorded upto a temperature of 1173 K.

The kinetics of the dehydration step were investigated by non-isothermal method. To arrive at the reaction model and kinetic parameters, the thermogravimetric data were analysed using ECIL TDC-316 (India) computer, applying appropriate equations commonly used in non-isothermal kinetic studies of decomposition reactions. The model giving best linear-fit for different equations by least-square error method was taken to be correct one.

Results and Discussion

Neodymium tartarate: Metal analysis of the compound revealed Nd, 36.39% (calcd. for Nd₂C₁₂H₁₂O₁₈·3H₂O, 36.67%). The infrared characteristic bands⁶ at 3 400, 1 590, 1 375 and ~1 100 cm⁻¹ (doublet) are assigned to ν_{O-H} (of water and secondary alcoholic groups), $\nu_{asym}(OCO)$, $\nu_{sym}(OCO)$ and ν_{C-OH} (doublet due to two dissimilar secondary alcoholic groups), respectively. A comparison with the infrared spectrum of d-tartaric acid suggests that two carboxylate and one secondary alcoholic groups are coordinated to Nd^{III} ion in the compound. On heating the compound to 494 K, the intensity of the band at 3 400 cm⁻¹ is considerably diminished due to the elimination of water molecules in the first step of decomposition.

The thermal decomposition of neodymium tartarate trihydrate occurs in four distinct steps as shown by TG curve and peaks in DTG curve (Fig. 1). The first step of decomposition of the compound starts at 331 K and continues upto 493 K. The weight loss during this step corresponds to the loss of three water molecules, suggesting the formation of anhydrous salt $\text{Nd}_2\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_{18}$ at this

Fig. 1. TG and DTG curves of neodymium tartarate

temperature. The temperature of maximum rate of dehydration is 352 K. The TG curve remains almost horizontal in the range 493–520 K, showing the stability of anhydrous salt within this range of temperature. The second step of decomposition starts above 520 K and a regular loss in weight occurs upto 632 K. The weight loss during this step corresponds to the partial conversion to the oxalate, $\text{Nd}_2\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_{18} \cdot \text{Nd}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3$, which remains stable upto 641 K. The third step of decomposition starts beyond 641 K and continues upto 812 K. The weight loss in this step corresponds to the formation of neodymium oxalate, $\text{Nd}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3$, which remains stable upto 830 K. The ultimate decomposition product neodymium oxide, Nd_2O_3 , is stable beyond 1104 K as no further loss in weight occurs on subsequent heating.

Gadolinium tartarate: On metal analysis, the compound was found to contain Gd, 35.86% (calcd. for $\text{Gd}_2\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_{18} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 35.56%). The infrared spectrum of the compound shows the expected bands at 3 350, 1 600, 1 390 and near $\sim 1 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (doublet) due to $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ (of water and secondary alcoholic groups), $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$, $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{C-OH}}$ (of two dissimilar secondary alcoholic groups), respectively. It is apparent that in this compound also two carboxylate and one secondary alcoholic groups are coordinated to Gd^{III} ion. There is a marked decrease in intensity of the band at $3 350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ when the compound is heated to 495 K due to the elimination of water molecules in the first step of decomposition.

The decomposition of gadolinium tartarate heptahydrate also occurs in four stages as shown by TG and DTG curves (Fig. 2). The first stage of decom-

position starts at 331 K and a regular loss in weight occurs upto 495 K. The weight loss during this

Fig. 2. TG and DTG curves of gadolinium tartarate.

stage corresponds to the elimination of seven molecules of water of crystallisation, leading to the formation of anhydrous salt, $\text{Gd}_2\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_{18}$. The rate of dehydration is maximum at 349 K. The slackening of the TG curve between 495 and 531 K suggests that the anhydrous salt remains stable in this range of temperature. The second stage of decomposition starts beyond 531 K and continues upto 621 K. The weight loss during this stage corresponds to the formation of gadolinium oxalate, $\text{Gd}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3$, which remains stable upto 631 K. The third stage of decomposition starting beyond 631 K gets completed at 763 K. The weight loss during this stage corresponds to the partial conversion to basic carbonate, $\text{Gd}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot \text{Gd}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3$. The curve remains horizontal from 763 to 808 K and suggests that the intermediate formed during this stage remains stable within this range of temperature. The fourth stage of decomposition is observed beyond 808 K and continues upto 1101 K. The weight loss at this stage corresponds to the formation of gadolinium oxide, Gd_2O_3 . However, no further loss in weight occurs during subsequent increase in temperature and the end product, Gd_2O_3 , remains stable beyond 1101 K.

Kinetics of decomposition: Non-isothermal kinetics of the first step of decomposition, *i.e.* the dehydration step has been studied. The values of the degree of decomposition (α), at different temperatures have been found from TG curve. From the value of α , appropriate $f(\alpha)$, *i.e.* $(1-\alpha)^n$ were calculated, where n depends upon the reaction model.

Corresponding values of $g(\alpha) = \int_0^\alpha \frac{d\alpha}{f(\alpha)}$, were also computed. The equations of Piloyan and Novikova⁷, Coats and Redfern⁸ and Horowitz and Metzger⁹ were applied. In the case of Piloyan–Novikova and Coats–Redfern equations, plots of $\log g(\alpha)/T^2$ vs $1/T$ were analysed, while for Horowitz–Metzger equation plots of $\log g(\alpha)$ vs θ were investigated ($\theta = T - T_m$: where, T = temperature and T_m = peak

temperature). The model which corresponds to the best linear-fit (having minimum least-square error) has been used to give the probable mechanism of decomposition. It is found that for both the compounds, the best linear-fit is obtained for the value of $g(\alpha) = -\ln(1-\alpha)$. The error is further reduced to an appreciable extent for α in the range 0.2–0.9. The plots obtained are shown in Figs. 3–5.

Fig. 3. Piloyan - Novikova plots: observed values for compounds of (★) Nd and (▲) Gd; calculated values for ideal straight line for compounds of (+) Nd and (⊗) Gd, neodymium tartarate (slope, -1.2665 , intercept, -1.2665 , 1st sqr, 0.0338 , E , $0.2949E+05$, Z , $0.3198 E+02$, ΔS^* , $-0.2175 E+03$, $X(\max)$, 0.0029 , $X(\min)$, 0.0027 ; bin X , 0.00001 ; $Y(\max)$, -5.4563 ; $Y(\min)$, -5.7921 , bin Y , 0.05), gadolinium tartarate (slope, -3562.0112 , intercept, 4.3186 ; 1st sqr, 0.0688 ; E , $0.6820 E+05$, Z , $0.2852 E+08$, ΔS^* , $-0.1035 E+03$, $X(\max)$, 0.0029 , $X(\min)$, 0.0027 , bin X , 0.00001 , $Y(\max)$, -5.1899 , $Y(\min)$, -5.4269 , bin Y , 0.05)

Fig. 4. Coats - Redfern plots: observed values for compounds of (★) Nd and (▲) Gd, calculated values for ideal straight line for compounds of (+) Nd and (⊗) Gd, neodymium tartarate (slope, -1.5110 ; 1st sqr, 0.9737 ; E , $0.2864 E+05$, Z , $0.1769 E+02$, ΔS^* , $-0.2224 E+03$, $X(\max)$, 0.0030 , $X(\min)$, 0.0020 ; bin X , 0.00001 ; $Y(\max)$, -4.3277 , $Y(\min)$, -6.0281 ; bin Y , 0.05); gadolinium tartarate (slope, -2015.3408 , intercept, -0.1017 ; 1st sqr, 0.8916 , E , $0.3859 E+05$, Z , $0.6119 E+03$, ΔS^* , $-0.1929 E+03$, $X(\max)$, 0.0030 ; $X(\min)$, 0.0021 ; bin X , 0.00001 , $Y(\max)$, -4.2784 ; $Y(\min)$, -6.7697 ; bin Y , 0.05).

Fig. 5. Horowitz - Metzger plots: observed values for compounds of (★) Nd and (▲) Gd, calculated values for ideal straight line for compounds of (+) Nd and (⊗) Gd, neodymium tartarate (slope, 0.0111 , intercept, -0.6473 , 1st sqr, 1.1619 , E , $0.2633 E+05$, Z , $0.3449 E+02$, ΔS^* , $-0.2169 E+03$, $X(\max)$, 142.7997 , $X(\min)$, -29.910 , bin X , 1.7271 , $Y(\max)$, 1.0611 , $Y(\min)$, -1.6773 , bin Y , 0.0456), gadolinium tartarate (slope, 0.0147 , intercept, -0.7444 , 1st sqr, 1.0520 , E , $0.3145 E+05$; Z , $0.8026 E+03$, ΔS^* , $-0.1906 E+03$, $X(\max)$, 118.200 ; $X(\min)$, -17.7997 , bin X , 1.96 , $Y(\max)$, 1.0611 , $Y(\min)$, 1.7288 , bin Y , 0.0465).

The values of slope, intercept and the energy of activation (E) were obtained directly from the computer. Also the values of pre-exponential factor (Z) from Piloyan - Novikova and Coats - Redfern methods were obtained directly. The values of Z in case of Horowitz - Metzger method were calculated using the equation,

$$Z = \frac{E}{RT_m} \beta \cdot \exp\left(\frac{E}{RT_m}\right)$$

and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) was obtained from the relation

$$Z = \frac{kT_m}{h} \exp\left(\frac{\Delta S^*}{R}\right)$$

where, R represents molar gas constant, β the rate of heating ($K s^{-1}$), k the Boltzmann constant and h the Planck constant. The values of kinetic parameters and the mechanism for which the best linear-fit was obtained by applying the above equations have been given in Table 1.

It is obvious that the values of various kinetic parameters obtained from different equations are reasonable and are in good agreement. It may be concluded that these tartarates have uniform decomposition pattern, dehydration being the first step and oxide being the end product. The dehydration step involves random nucleation mechanism¹⁰. The small negative values of ΔS^* indicate that the transition state involved in the decomposition process has a more ordered structure, perhaps there is some agglomeration of particles before the start of random nucleation.

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	Compd.	Equation	E kJ mol ⁻¹	Z s ⁻¹	ΔS^* JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	Model*
1.	Nd ₂ O ₃ ·H ₂ O _{1.8} ·3H ₂ O	Piloyan-Novikova	29.487	3.198 × 10 ²	-217.489	—
		Coats-Redfern	28.645	1.769 × 10 ²	-222.411	R.N.
		Horowitz-Metzger	26.333	3.449 × 10 ²	-216.871	R.N.
2.	Gd ₂ O ₃ ·H ₂ O _{1.8} ·7H ₂ O	Piloyan-Novikova	68.205	2.852 × 10 ²	-103.509	—
		Coats-Redfern	88.589	6.119 × 10 ²	-192.855	R.N.
		Horowitz-Metzger	84.449	8.028 × 10 ²	-190.630	R.N.

* R.N. = Random nucleation.

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